

Impact of Government Investments in Education on the Growth of its Economy: A Study of 33 OECD Countries through Panel Co-integration

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Abstract: This study aims at looking into the long-term impact of a country's governmental expenditure in education on its economic development. It was carried out using the data obtained from 33 OECD countries over a 20-year period starting 1995. The data were analyzed through a combination of tests including such tests as Panel Unit Root and Panel Cointegration and estimators such as Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares and Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares. The results show a positive correlation between the two, and even the findings drawn from the FMOLS and DOLS estimators show that the relationship is positive and significant.

Keywords: Government Expenditure on Education, Economic Growth, OECD, Panel Data, Cointegration, OECD

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1. Introduction

Education is considered to be the most significant of all the investments in human capital, which has been extensively studied. It is one of the most important tools to excel and prosper in case of any economy. The growth engine can be driven faster with new ideas, technologies and discoveries, ultimately resulting in innovations for the upliftment of the economy in specific and mankind in general. The phenomenon of privatization is changing the market scenario in most of the countries and gradually education is turning out to be a luxury and becoming unaffordable to a common man. The statement of Amartya Sen,

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(1999) in his work "Development as Freedom", "*Education has both intrinsic and instrumental value; it is not only for the individual but also for the society as a whole*" clearly shows how important education is. In fact, the spending on education is regarded a one of the significant socioeconomic development indicators.

Social benefits from the education in producing skilled individuals, who, in turn, contribute to the country's developmental process, have been investigated by many researchers in the recent past. The ultimate social benefits which are enjoyed from education clearly show the need to increase the public expenditure on it. However, a great debate over the variations in the public and private expenditure on education in most of the economies has been going on.

From the theoretical view, varied opinions can be seen with respect to the newly-developed models that help understand growth such as Solow (1956) and Swan (1956), which don't incorporate the role played by the investments made by governments in providing quality education in the economic growth while explaining the growth process. The role of the fiscal policy in this regard is looked at only on the basis of the maximum output it could generate rather than the long-run growth rate, which it could lead to. Besides, the state can register a steady growth rate due to such external factors as population growth and technological advancements. In the neo classical model, fiscal policy is thought to impact a state's transformation to the steady growth. Meanwhile, the endogenous growth models look into how consistent public investments in developing a skilled workforce lead to a consistent growth rate, as envisaged from the works of Barro (1990) and Lucas (1990), which do provide the mechanisms to study how a country's fiscal policy can influence its level of productivity and its economy's stable growth rate. In this connection, the present study makes an attempt to testify if the Public Expenditure on Education will have any impact on the long-terms growth prospects of a country through the data obtained from a group of 33 OECD countries during 1995-2015.

2. Review of Current Studies

There has been a considerable chunk of research carried out in the focus area, which has looked into the contributions made by a state's thrust into education to its economic growth. It also explored how fiscal policies contributed to the growth process. In the paper, such studies are reviewed. Such studies as Romer, (1986) Levine and Renelt, (1992) Mankiw et al., (1992) Barro and Lee, (1993) proved the fact that investments into quality education in a country's contribute positively to its growth process.

In case of the expenditure of a government on education, Kneller et al (1998) examined a group of 22 OECD countries for the period of during 1970-95. The study classified the Public Expenditure on Education as a productive expenditure on the line of the

expenditure on defense, health, housing, and transport. It proved that the Government expenditure on education resulted in the augmentation of the growth process. Landau (1983) made an extensive study of 104 countries for the period of 1960-86 by dividing countries on low, middle and higher income countries. The study found negative interrelation between the Government spending in education and the growth of its economy in terms of its GDP. Besides, in case of lower income countries, a higher expenditure was found to correlate with lower growth rates. Barrow (2001), on examining the data taken from a group of one hundred countries over 30 years from 1965 to 1995, found that growth is related positively to the number of years that people spend in the attainment of school certificates at primary and secondary levels. Chandra (2010) examined the Government Expenditure on Education in India over an almost six-decade period from 1951-2009, and found a bi-directional impact between both the variables.

3. Data and Methodology

This research paper adopts uses a balanced data taken from a panel of 33 OECD countries over almost two decades, i.e., from 1995 to 2015. (The remaining OECD countries are leftover because of the inconsistency in the data obtained). The study uses two variables Government's Expenditure in Education in terms of its GDP percentage (*exped*) and Real GDP Per Capita (Constant 2010 US\$) (*rgdpp*), which is used as an indicator to measure the growth of a country's economy. Both the indicators have been extracted from the UNESCO to access the statistics and from and the World Bank to understand its World Development Indicators. Notwithstanding the availability of the data for much earlier period than the period set for this study, to achieve consistency in the data to be obtained from these countries, the time-period has been restricted to 1995 to 2015. Interpolation technique has been used to sort out the dataset to fill the missing gaps. The data has been converted into natural log values to smoothen the estimation process and the variables will be represented by *lnrgdpp* and *lnexped* in all further processes hereby.

In this study, three-unit root tests, namely, Im, Pesaran and Shin, Fisher- ADF Test, Levin, Lin and Chu were used to measure the stationarity of the data. These tests will be complemented by the Johansen fisher panel cointegration test, which helped find out the relationship between the variables over a period of time. In addition, the estimators mentioned above have been employed to measure the functioning of the cointegrating vector in the long run. All the tests have been carried out by Eviews 10 and Stata 14.

4. Empirical Analysis of Results

All the variables which are used in the test are found to be stationary in the first difference (Table 1), which forms to be the pre-condition for the testing of cointegration.

4.1. Panel Unit Root Tests

4.1.1. Levin, Lin, and Chu

Levin, Lin, and Chu (LLC) unit root test employs a null hypothesis mentioned hereunder:

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \alpha Y_{it-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_1} \beta_{ij} \Delta Y_{it-j} + X'_{it} \delta + \epsilon_{it} \tag{1}$$

Where it assumes $\alpha = \rho - 1$, however it lets the fixed order for the terms of difference, p_i , which differ from one section to the other. This test includes the following null and alternative hypotheses:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0: \alpha &= 0 \\ H_1: \alpha &< 0 \end{aligned}$$

Between the two, the null hypothesis has a unit root whereas the alternative hypothesis doesn't.

4.1.2. Im, Pesaran and Shin

It deploys exclusive ADF regressions at all sections that cross one another, which is given here under.

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_1} \beta_{ij} \Delta y_{it-j} + X'_{it} \delta + \epsilon_{it} \tag{2}$$

The null hypothesis is codified as:

$$H_0: \alpha_i = 0 \quad \text{for all } i$$

On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis is codified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i &= 0 && \text{for all } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N_1 \\ H_1: \alpha_i &< 0 && \text{for } i = N+1, N+2, \dots, N \end{aligned}$$

4.1.3. Fisher-ADF Test

This test, promulgated by Maddala and Wu based on the Fisher (1932), who criticized the Pesaran et al. (2003) unit root test for its complexity in its real-world applications, and cross-correlations, employs a combination of the p-values which are a culmination of the test statistic applied for unit roots in all the remaining cross-sectional units. It is a test which does not follow the set parameters.

$$-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \log(\pi_i) \rightarrow X^2_2 N \tag{3}$$

The application of these tests proved the fact that the variables are non-stationary at Levels I (0) as they turned out to be stationary at First Differences I (1). The results were tabulated below.

Table 1: Results of Unit Root Test

Variable	Statistics	At level		At First Difference		Inference
		I&T	NONE	I&T	NONE	
Rgdpp	LLC	-1.56665 (0.0586)	15.4152 (1.0000)	-2.20111** (0.0139)	-11.3612* (0.0000)	I (1)
	IPS	0.83589 (0.7984)	-	-7.72862* (0.0000)	-	I (1)
	ADF	52.3109 (0.8900)	2.35882 (1.0000)	180.365* (0.0000)	239.244* (0.0000)	I (1)
Exped	LLC	6.25969 (1.0000)	0.01309 (0.5052)	10.6069 (1.0000)	-10.1630 (0.0000)	I (1)
	IPS	-1.11167 (0.1331)	-	-3.55077* (0.0002)	-	I (1)
	ADF	70.9786 (0.3154)	31.8832 (0.9999)	104.897* (0.0016)	286.340 (0.0000)	I (1)

Notes: * means statistically noteworthy at the level of 1%, ** means statistically noteworthy at the level of 5 %. Values in brackets show p-values, I denotes intercept and T denotes trend.

Table 1 presents the statistics obtained from the tests for the variables at the two levels and their first differences. When measured, the prescribed levels are non-stationary as the values of the test statistics, i.e., LLC, IPS, and ADF are not significant. But when these variables are measured in first differences, LLC, IPS, and ADF statistics are found to be statistically significant. Hence, it is necessary to further proceed to Johansen Fisher panel cointegration test to find out if there is any long-term relationship between the variables.

4.2. Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration

It is used as an alternative approach to test the Panel Co-integration, which is a combination of different tests taken from single cross sections to get the statistics for the full panel. It works on the basis of the overall p-values of the single values from its eigenvalues and trace statistics. Meanwhile, in case π_i is taken to be the p-value of a single cointegration test for cross-section i , the null hypothesis can be:

$$-2 \sum_{i=1}^N \log(\pi_i) \rightarrow X^2_N$$

Table 2: Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)	Probability	Fisher Statistics (from max-eigen test)	Probability
None	215.4	0.0000	193.6	0.0000
At most 1	81.69	0.0921	81.69	0.0921

Table 3: Results of Each Cross Section Results

	Trace Test		Max-Eigen Test	
Cross Section	Statistics	Prob.**	Statistics	Prob.**
Null Cointegration Hypothesis				
Australia	25.1362	0.0615	16.7434	0.1162
Austria	18.4609	0.3138	13.3977	0.2970
Belgium	33.3395	0.0049	22.3136	0.0182
Canada	24.1738	0.0802	17.2130	0.1007
Chile	17.7469	0.3612	12.8246	0.3424
Czech	18.0627	0.3397	13.2616	0.3074
Denmark	37.8054	0.0010	30.3564	0.0009
Estonia	21.0994	0.1753	15.8855	0.1502
Finland	32.8850	0.0057	24.0471	0.0097
France	36.8304	0.0015	21.8189	0.0217
Germany	28.1220	0.0258	16.9128	0.1104
Greece	30.6520	0.0117	25.5373	0.0056
Hungary	18.4303	0.3157	11.9968	0.4155
Iceland	25.4585	0.0562	18.4357	0.0683
Ireland	35.7518	0.0021	22.6606	0.0161
Israel	14.4344	0.6216	10.4633	0.5694
Italy	17.8851	0.3517	13.2334	0.3096
Japan	51.5383	0.0000	44.8243	0.0000
Korea	17.2945	0.3933	14.1019	0.2474
Luxembourg	25.8359	0.0505	17.1029	0.1041
Mexico	30.1392	0.0138	22.4044	0.0177
Netherlands	29.6784	0.0160	19.9602	0.0413
New Zealand	26.3064	0.0442	18.1442	0.0750
Norway	27.0618	0.0354	22.4407	0.0174
Poland	24.8719	0.0662	21.5874	0.0236
Portugal	23.6893	0.0913	13.7978	0.2680
Slovakia	26.9290	0.0368	23.2921	0.0128
Slovenia	13.2548	0.7181	6.8065	0.9134
Spain	32.4782	0.0065	24.6676	0.0077
Sweden	26.5912	0.0407	17.2173	0.1005
Switzerland	21.9826	0.1414	14.1049	0.2472
Turkey	22.5583	0.1224	14.5656	0.2183
UK	18.1533	0.3337	11.7388	0.4399

Table 3 continued

Hypothesis of at most 1 Cointegration Relationship				
Australia	8.3928	0.2213	8.3928	0.2213
Austria	5.0632	0.5873	5.0632	0.5873
Belgium	11.0258	0.0876	11.0258	0.0876
Canada	6.9607	0.3486	6.9607	0.3486
Chile	4.9223	0.6076	4.9223	0.6076
Czech	4.8011	0.6251	4.8011	0.6251
Denmark	7.4491	0.3000	7.4491	0.3000
Estonia	5.2140	0.5660	5.2140	0.5660
Finland	8.8380	0.1906	8.8380	0.1906
France	15.0115	0.0187	15.0115	0.0187
Germany	11.2092	0.0819	11.2092	0.0819
Greece	5.1147	0.5800	5.1147	0.5800
Hungary	6.4335	0.4073	6.4335	0.4073
Iceland	7.0228	0.3422	7.0228	0.3422
Ireland	13.0912	0.0401	13.0912	0.0401
Israel	3.9711	0.7463	3.9711	0.7463
Italy	4.6517	0.6469	4.6517	0.6469
Japan	6.7140	0.3753	6.7140	0.3753
Korea	3.1926	0.8529	3.1926	0.8529
Luxembourg	8.7330	0.1974	8.7330	0.1974
Mexico	7.7348	0.2741	7.7348	0.2741
Netherlands	9.7182	0.1406	9.7182	0.1406
Newzealand	8.1622	0.2387	8.1622	0.2387
Norway	4.6212	0.6513	4.6212	0.6513
Poland	3.2845	0.8411	3.2845	0.8411
Portugal	9.8914	0.1322	9.8914	0.1322
Slovakia	3.6369	0.7938	3.6369	0.7938
Slovenia	6.4482	0.4056	6.4482	0.4056
Spain	7.8106	0.2675	7.8106	0.2675
Sweden	9.3739	0.1586	9.3739	0.1586
Switzerland	7.8776	0.2618	7.8776	0.2618
Turkey	7.9927	0.2523	7.9927	0.2523
UK	6.4144	0.4096	6.4144	0.4096

Notes: **MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

From Table 3, it is clear that the null hypothesis of zero cointegration can be refuted at most 1cointegration equations, which shows that only one cointegration equation is present, which points to a robust cointegration between the Government Expenditure on

Education in terms of GDP percentage and the Economic Development, which is calculated by the Real GDP Per Capita (constant US\$2010).

The Individual Cross Section results (Table 3) show the long-term relationship between the public spending on education and the country’s growth rate. It is shown in almost all countries except France and Ireland – in France, the P-value of (0.0187) denies that there can be no relationship between the variables in the long run and in case of Ireland, it is found to be (0.0401).

4.3. Panel FMOLS and DOLS

Having found a strong relationship between how much a government spends on education and its contribution to the growth of its economy, we then proceeded to estimate the long-run cointegrating vector between the two variables using Panel FMOLS and Panel DOLS with pooled weighted estimation method. The Panel DOLS method is used to confirm the assumption that one lag and one lead occur in the change of the regressors. The Tables 4 and 5 contain the results obtained from the panel FMOLS and DOLS estimators for all the 33 sample countries.

Table 4: Panel Fully Modified Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNEXPED	0.390795	0.069753	5.602524	0.0000
R-squared	0.963496	Mean dependent var		10.30621
Adjusted R-squared	0.961572	S.D. dependent var		0.647748
S.E. of regression	0.126978	Sum squared resid		10.09331
Long-run variance	0.038534			

Table 5: Panel Dynamic Least Squares

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNEXPED	0.335899	0.083614	4.017271	0.0001
R-squared	0.975342	Mean dependent var		10.31094
Adjusted R-squared	0.968282	S.D. dependent var		0.646115
S.E. of regression	0.115070	Sum squared resid		6.104177
Long-run variance	0.024384			

Tables 4 and 5 prove that the coefficients in both FMOLS and DOLS are significant at 1% level, which shows a positive long-standing relationship between the two variables. The results obtained from FMOLS suggest that if we increase the government expenditure on education by at least once percent, it can affect an increase of 0.39 percent in GDP while

the results of the panel DOLS suggest 0.33 percent GDP increase for the same. On the whole, it can be concluded that the government expenditure on education will have a positive impact on its economy.

5. Conclusion

The study aimed at confirming if there is any durable impact of the government spending on education on its GDP in terms of its percentage growth, using data taken from 33 OECD nations for a 20-year period starting from 1995-2015. The tests were conducted through the panel unit root tests, panel cointegration tests and Panel FMOLS and Panel DOLS. The panel cointegration test results demonstrated a positive relationship between the two variables for the selected countries. The findings of FMOLS and DOLS suggest that if the government enhances its spending on education, it will also enhance its GDP. Apart from the growth, such an investment will help governments reap many social benefits such as a significant decrease in the crime rates, etc. In this regard, the changing scenario of privatization of the education system should also be reviewed in order to make education affordable to all classes of the society and to reap the benefits of innovations for the upliftment of the mankind.

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